

Dynamic Compressive Properties of Lightweight Rubberized Concrete

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Abstract

This study experimentally examines the dynamic characteristics of concrete made of waste car tyres as both fine and coarse aggregates (rubberized concrete), resulting in light-weight concrete with the densities of 2350 kg/m³, 2091 kg/m³, and 1833 kg/m³ for 0%, 15%, and 30% rubber content, respectively. The dynamic compressive characteristic of the rubberized concrete was quantified by using a Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar equipment up to the strain rate of 182 s⁻¹. The experimental results have consistently shown excellent impact resistance of rubberized concrete as compared to that of normal concrete, including the progressive failure, crack propagation and normalized energy absorption. Under the same impact, rubberized concrete was still almost intact while normal concrete was fragmented into pieces. Rubberized concrete significantly slowed down the crack propagation and exhibited progressive failure as compared to normal concrete. The compressive strength and axial strain at maximum dynamic stress of rubberized concrete are sensitive to the strain rate and the sensitivity increases with the rubber content. Young's modulus of rubberized concrete showed inconsistent strain rate sensitivity. Meanwhile, rubberized concrete was more sensitive to the strain rate than normal concrete. In addition, new equations to estimate the DIFs of rubberized concrete with different rubber contents were proposed, in which the lateral inertia confinement effect was removed.

Keywords: Rubberized concrete; Strain rate; SHPB; Impact loading; Energy absorption.

30 **Introduction**

31 Disposal of waste tyre rubber has become an environmental issue of great concern. Rubber
32 crumbs can be used to replace aggregates in concrete for construction, which have been
33 investigated in previous studies [1-6]. Rubberized concrete (RuC) is an environmental-friendly
34 material, which has a similar ingredient as conventional concrete with coarse aggregates
35 partially replaced by rubber aggregates. Owing to the existence of rubber, the rubberized
36 concrete is much lighter than conventional concrete. Elchalakani [2] reported that the
37 rubberized concrete with 40% rubber content has the density of 1950 kg/m^3 , which is lower
38 than 2450 kg/m^3 of conventional concrete. It was reported that the rubberized concrete exhibits
39 lower compressive strength but higher energy absorption capacity with the increasing rubber
40 content [3, 4]. Rubberized concrete has good energy absorption capacity against impact loads,
41 as demonstrated in the previous studies [7, 8]. Given the sound energy absorption capacity,
42 rubberized concrete has been applied in the fields of roadside barriers and blocks [2, 7, 9, 10].
43 The roadside barriers made of rubberized concrete can mitigate the injury risk to drivers and
44 passengers by reducing the impact force and acceleration.

45 Various impact tests were conducted to study energy absorption capacity of rubberized
46 concrete under dynamic loading. Recently, Pham et al. [11] studied the impact performance of
47 RuC columns. It was demonstrated that the column using rubberized concrete has much higher
48 energy absorption capacity under impact loading. With the rubber content changed from 0% to
49 30%, the impact energy absorption capacity of the column increased by 63%. The displacement
50 experienced by the RuC columns was nearly double than that of the plain concrete column
51 before failure. Gupta et al. [12] conducted impact tests on rubberized concrete with 25% rubber
52 fiber by drop-weight and reported the increased energy absorption by adding rubber content.
53 As reported by Donga et al. [13], adding rubber can enhance impact resistance capacity of RuC

54 by up to 60%. Atahan and Yücel [14] conducted impact tests on rubberized concrete by using
55 Instron machine. It was reported that the peak impact force can be effectively reduced and the
56 impact duration can be prolonged by using rubberized concrete. Pham et al. [15] also conducted
57 drop-weight tests on rubberized concrete cylinders along the axial direction. The peak impact
58 force can be reduced by 50% and the impact duration can be prolonged by using RuC. It was
59 also found that the impact resistance can be further improved by confining RuC cylinders via
60 FRP sheets. Since RuC has potential applications for the impact energy absorption, it is
61 essential to understand its mechanical properties such as compressive strength, strain, energy
62 absorption, and modulus under dynamic loads.

63 Intensive studies on compressive properties of concrete and concrete-like materials have been
64 conducted under intermediate and high strain rates [16-20]. It is well known that concrete
65 experiences different behaviors under quasi-static and dynamic loads due to the strain rate
66 effect, which has been intensively documented [21, 22]. Dynamic behaviors of concrete are
67 affected by the inertial effect [16] and the viscosity effect (also known as Stefan effect) [23,
68 24]. For instance, owing to the viscosity effect, the development of micro-cracks is suppressed
69 under dynamic loading [23, 25]. The effect of strain rate on concrete mechanical properties
70 such as strength, strain and Young's modulus has been revealed and the mechanical properties
71 of concrete at high strain rate are also affected by the shape and content of coarse aggregates
72 [26]. Dynamic increase factor (DIF), defined as the ratio of dynamic compressive strength with
73 respect to quasi-static compressive strength, can be used to quantify the strength enhancement
74 under different strain rates. Some empirical formulae [27-29] were proposed to determine the
75 compressive strength DIF for conventional concrete. The DIF formulae were also proposed to
76 reveal the strain rate effect on conventional concrete at the elevated temperature [30]. In
77 addition, the effects of the factors such as various aggregates, end friction confinement and

78 lateral inertial confinement on the dynamic compressive properties were studied by Hao et al.
79 [31].

80 Rubberized concrete has similar ingredients as conventional concrete except for the inclusion
81 of rubber aggregates. Therefore, RuC and conventional concrete might have different
82 mechanical properties. The quasi-static mechanical properties of RuC have been well
83 investigated [32, 33]. However, the study on the dynamic compressive properties of rubberized
84 concrete is very limited. Liu et al. [34] conducted SHPB tests on rubberized concrete to study
85 its dynamic properties. It was reported that the rubberized concrete has a lower DIF than the
86 conventional concrete. The rubberized concrete exhibited the increasing energy absorption
87 capacity with the rubber content within 10%. Whereas, the rubberized concrete experienced
88 the opposite trend when the rubber content is over 10%.

89 In this study, a total of 33 rubberized concrete specimens were prepared with partial aggregate
90 replaced by rubber crumbs. Three rubber contents were 0%, 15 % and 30% with respect to the
91 total volume of aggregates. Both quasi-static and dynamic tests were carried out to investigate
92 the effect of rubber content on the compressive strength of RuC. Dynamic tests were carried
93 out by using Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) to obtain the dynamic compressive strength
94 with the strain rate up to 182 s^{-1} . Failure mode, dynamic strength and energy absorption
95 capacity were compared and analysed. The formulae of the dynamic increase factor (DIF) were
96 derived accordingly.

97 **Experimental program**

98 *Mixture design and pre-treatment method*

99 Rubberized concrete consists of mortar matrix, traditional and rubber aggregates, and additive.
100 Three RuC mixes were prepared with three rubber contents (i.e. 0%, 15 %, and 30%). The

101 details of RuC are given in Table 1 [35]. Two sets of coarse aggregates with maximum size of
102 10 mm and 7 mm were used in the concrete mix and silica sand was used as fine aggregates.
103 The rubber crumbs had three sets of size 1-3 mm, 3-5 mm (to partially replace fine aggregate)
104 and 5-10 mm (to partially replace coarse aggregate). It is noted that the replacement of both
105 fine and coarse aggregates was adopted according to previous studies [36, 37]. These studies
106 suggested that using a combination of fine and coarse rubber aggregates results a higher
107 strength than those with a single type of rubber aggregates. The physical properties of crumb
108 rubber are given in Table 2 [2]. Concrete mixes were prepared in accordance with AS 1012.2
109 [38]. According to the previous studies [11, 15], the maximum rubber content of 30% was
110 chosen in order to achieve acceptable compressive strengths. When the rubber content is over
111 30%, increasing rubber content can lead to rubberized concrete with low strength, i.e. less than
112 10 MPa. The mix design was adopted from the previous study to reach the static compressive
113 strength of 45 MPa, 25 MPa and 15 MPa for the rubberized concrete with the rubber contents
114 of 0%, 15% and 30%, respectively.

115 To improve the mechanical properties of RuC and the bonding between water cement surfaces,
116 water soaking treatment was conducted before the RuC mixing. The water soaking treatment
117 consists of washing rubber aggregates with water and soaking them in water for 24 hours to
118 reduce the rubber hydrophobicity. This treatment method was chosen due to its simplicity as
119 compared to the treatment with alkaline solution of NaOH as reported in the previous study
120 [39]. The test results showed a minor variation in the compressive strengths of concrete when
121 using these two different treatment methods as reported in the previous study [39]. The slump
122 test on the rubberized concrete was also carried out and the slump in this study was in the range
123 of 130-150 mm to ensure the workability of concrete mixes.

124 ***Test matrix and material properties***

125 The specimens were well prepared and tested for each concrete mix (i.e. 0%, 15%, and 30%),
126 in which rubber aggregates were uniformly distributed in the samples as shown in Fig. 1. A
127 total of 9 cylindrical specimens with a diameter of $\text{\O}100$ mm and a length of 200 mm
128 ($\text{\O}100\text{mm}-200\text{mm}$) were prepared for the quasi-static compressive tests. Three cylindrical
129 specimens were tested for each rubber content. The quasi-static compressive strength can be
130 used to calculate the DIF of compressive strength. A total of 24 cylindrical specimens with a
131 diameter of $\text{\O}100$ mm and a length of 50 mm ($\text{\O}100\text{mm}-50\text{mm}$) were prepared for SHPB
132 compressive tests. For each rubber content, four different loading rates were used and two
133 identical specimens were tested at each loading rate. The L/D ratio of 0.5 was applied to
134 minimise the lateral inertial confinement in SHPB tests. The specimens were ground at both
135 sides with the surface roughness less than 0.02 mm to minimize non-perfect contact and the
136 frictional effect between the specimen and bars.

137 Quasi-static compression test was conducted according to AS 1012.9 [40]. The concrete
138 samples with the size $\text{\O}100\text{mm}-200\text{mm}$ were tested by using MATEST equipment as shown
139 in Fig. 2 (L). The loading rate was 0.333 MPa/s, which corresponded to the quasi-static strain
140 rate of 1×10^{-4} /s.

141 ***Impact Testing Procedure***

142 Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) system with a diameter of 100 mm was used to conduct
143 dynamic material tests. SHPB system has been widely used to obtain dynamic material
144 properties [20, 41]. The dynamic properties including failure progress, failure patterns,
145 compressive strength and energy absorption capacity can be obtained from the testing data.

146 As shown in Fig. 2 (R), $\text{\O}100\text{mm}$ SHPB system consists of an incident bar with the length of
147 5500 mm and a transmitted bar with the length of 3000 mm. The $\text{\O}100\text{mm}$ bars were made of
148 stainless steels with density, Young's modulus and elastic wave velocity of 7800 kg/m^3 , 240

149 GPa and 5064 m/s, respectively. Grease was applied at the specimen–bar interfaces before tests
 150 to minimize the end friction confinement. A pulse shaper was mounted on the impact end of
 151 the incident bar to obtain the half-sine stress waveform. The pulse shaper could also extend the
 152 rising time of the incident pulse, which makes the stress equilibrium easier to be achieved.
 153 Circular rubber pulse shapers, which had a thickness of 3 mm and a radius of 20 mm, were
 154 used in this study for all the tests. A high-speed camera was used to record the failure progress
 155 of the specimens. All the RuC specimens with different rubber contents were tested at various
 156 pressures.

157 As per the theory of one-dimensional stress wave propagation, the stress (σ), strain rate ($\dot{\varepsilon}$)
 158 and strain (ε) of the specimen are derived based on the measured reflected wave (ε_R) and
 159 transmitted wave (ε_T) [42], namely

$$160 \quad \sigma(t) = E \left(\frac{A}{A_s} \right) \varepsilon_T(t) \quad (1)$$

$$161 \quad \dot{\varepsilon}(t) = -\frac{2C_0}{L} \varepsilon_R \quad (2)$$

$$162 \quad \varepsilon(t) = \int_0^T \dot{\varepsilon}(t) dt \quad (3)$$

163 where L and A_s are the length and the cross section area of the tested specimen, respectively.
 164 A , E and C_0 are the cross-section area, Young's Modulus and the elastic wave velocity of the
 165 bars, respectively. The data is valid only when the stress equilibrium is achieved. Therefore,
 166 the stress equilibrium was checked for all the specimens. In this study, the strain rate is
 167 determined when the peak value of the strain rate plateau is achieved.

168 **Experimental results and discussions**

169 *Compressive and tensile strengths under quasi-static tests*

170 Quasi-static compression tests on rubberized concrete cylinders (100x200 mm) were carried
171 out to estimate the compressive strength at 28 days. The compressive strengths of rubberized
172 concrete with 0%, 15%, and 30% rubber content were 56.33 MPa (SD = 1.65), 27.96 MPa (SD
173 = 0.09), and 16.33 MPa (SD = 1.55), respectively. The compressive strength of rubberized
174 concrete reduced with an increase with the rubber content because of the poor bonding between
175 the cement paste and rubber particles in the interfacial transition zone (ITZ) as also reported in
176 previous studies [2, 34, 43]. The split tensile strength of the tested specimens for 0%, 15%, and
177 30% rubber content was 4.42 MPa, 2.55 MPa, and 2.16 MPa, respectively. It is worth
178 mentioning that the measured density of 0%, 15%, and 30% rubberized concrete was
179 respectively 2350 kg/m³, 2091 kg/m³, and 1833 kg/m³.

180 In quasi-static compression tests, normal concrete failed in a more explosive manner as
181 compared to the rubberized concrete which retained its original shape with cracks extended
182 through the height of the specimens. The same manner was observed in the in-direct tensile
183 tests where normal concrete was split into halves while rubberized concrete remained almost
184 intact.

185 ***Validity and strain-rate determination of SHPB tests***

186 The dynamic compressive strength of rubberized concrete was derived from the testing results
187 by using the SHPB. It is worth mentioning that the dynamic compressive strength is only valid
188 when the stress equilibrium condition is achieved for the testing. Therefore, the stress
189 equilibrium was checked for all the tested specimens after removing the time lag and only those
190 satisfy the equilibrium condition were included in this study. It is noted that rubber pulse
191 shapers were used in these tests as suggested by the previous study by Khan et al. [41] to
192 eliminate the high-frequency oscillation and achieve the stress equilibrium. Fig. 3 shows the
193 stresses including the incident stress, reflected stress, transmitted stress and the sum of the

194 incident and reflected stresses in three specimens which represent the rubber concrete with
195 various rubber contents (0%, 15 %, and 30%). As shown in Fig. 3, the sum of the incident and
196 reflected stresses reasonably matched with the transmitted stress, demonstrating all the tests
197 achieved the equilibrium condition. The variation at the peak stress between the reflected wave
198 versus the sum of the incident and reflected waves less than 5% was adopted in this study
199 according to a suggestion from the previous study [44].

200 It was observed that the strain-rate of the tested specimen varied with time. Therefore, the
201 strain-rate during the effective loading period cannot be considered as a constant, which was
202 also discussed in previous studies [18, 19, 45]. There have been a few methods of determining
203 the representative strain-rate for a given test result, i.e. Grote et al. [18] used the mean value
204 for the strain-rate during the loading period while Zhang et al. [19] recommended that the
205 strain-rate at the failure point should be used as the representative strain rate. In this study, the
206 strain-rate was determined at the maximum compressive stress in the sample as shown in Fig.
207 4. This definition was used in previous studies to determine the strain-rate of SHPB specimens
208 [19, 45].

209 *Failure processes and failure modes*

210 The progressive failure of all the specimens was recorded by using a high-speed camera. Fig.
211 5 shows the progressive failure of the specimens with different rubber contents. Cracks initiated
212 from both sides of the specimens and developed into the mid region. This observation again
213 confirmed the stress equilibrium was achieved in these samples. Afterwards, some more cracks
214 initiated within the mid-region and developed arbitrarily. It can be seen that rubberized
215 concrete developed cracks earlier than that of normal concrete due to its lower static
216 compressive strength, i.e. 15% rubberized concrete showed 10 minor cracks at 50 μ s while
217 only two minor cracks were found on the normal concrete at 60 μ s. However, rubberized

218 concrete slowed down the crack development as shown in Fig. 5. The number of cracks in 15%
219 rubberized concrete at 200 μs was less than that of the normal concrete at the same time instant.
220 The number of cracks in the 15% rubberized concrete specimen at 1800 μs was still even less
221 than that of normal concrete at 200 μs . Eventually, normal concrete was shattered into small
222 pieces because of its brittle nature while 15% rubberized concrete specimen broke into
223 relatively larger pieces. Unfortunately, the progressive failure of 30% rubberized concrete was
224 not properly recorded.

225 Under the high loading rate, it could be seen that the control sample exploded into pieces
226 indicating the brittle collapse. However, for rubberized concrete, especially at higher strain
227 rate, it experienced less brittle damage and such damage propagated from the edges then
228 towards the centre of the specimen as shown in Fig. 5. When stress increased, cracks start to
229 propagate and rubber tends to resist the crack from expanding, i.e. it acts as a crack arrestor.
230 The previous study has shown that the difference in the elastic moduli between rubber and
231 concrete may lead to a reduction in the crack velocity [46] because of the damping effect of
232 rubber. So overall it shows that the increase in the rubber content enhances the impact
233 resistance of rubberized concrete.

234 The final failure modes of the rubberized specimens were very different with various rubber
235 contents and strain rates as shown in Fig. 6. It can be seen that the normal concrete at the strain
236 rate of 116 s^{-1} was disintegrated into numerous fragments and with the increase in the strain
237 rate it shattered into even smaller pieces. This failure mode of normal concrete was also
238 consistent with the experimental results reported in the previous studies [19, 44, 45, 47].
239 Meanwhile, rubberized concrete with 15% and 30% rubber contents showed better behaviour
240 under high impact loads. The 15% rubberized concrete exhibited larger fragments under similar
241 strain rate as compared to the normal concrete as shown in Fig. 6. For instance, under the strain

242 rate of 103 s^{-1} , 15% rubber concrete failed from the edges but the middle part was still intact.
243 For 30% rubberized concrete, only small cracks appeared on the circumference and the
244 specimen fairly kept its cylindrical shape with much less fragments. As the strain rate increased
245 to 125 s^{-1} , the normal concrete was shattered into smaller pieces while the 15% rubberized
246 concrete only broke into a few large pieces. At the same strain rate, 30% rubberized concrete
247 outperformed the former two specimens and only the outer edge was slightly damaged. Even
248 at the higher strain rate of 151 s^{-1} the 30% rubberized concrete specimen showed cracks near
249 the circumference region while the middle part was still intact. This observation shows that the
250 damage of rubberized concrete under impact loads reduces with the increase in the rubber
251 content and the difference becomes more apparent with 30% rubber content. In the meantime,
252 the increase of the loading rate (strain-rate) significantly affected the failure mode of normal
253 concrete but it showed less influence on the rubberized concrete. The excellent performance of
254 rubberized concrete can be explained as follows: (1) due to the crack arresting characteristic of
255 rubber aggregates as reported in the previous study [46] and (2) bridging effect of coarse rubber
256 aggregates between cracks as they elongate between the cracks reducing the intensity of cracks
257 [48]. This finding suggests that rubberized concrete is highly suitable for structures subjected
258 to impact or blast loadings.

259 *Stress-strain curves and energy absorption*

260 To investigate the dynamic compressive strength, stress-strain curves of different specimens
261 under various strain rates are derived from the testing data. Figs. 7-9 show the stress-strain
262 curves of the specimens with various rubber contents at different strain rates. It can be seen
263 that the compressive strengths of all the concrete mixes increase with the strain rate. This
264 observation supports the previous understanding of the strain rate effect on the concrete-like
265 materials [19, 47, 49]. When concrete-like materials are subjected to high impact loads, the

266 induced cracks more likely propagate through shorter and straighter paths which cut through
267 stronger sections, i.e. coarse aggregates, and thus result in a higher strength. Whereas, in static
268 testing, cracks in concrete usually form at weak sections and then connect together, leading to
269 failure. The induced cracks are thus long and have an arbitrary path. Dynamic increase factor
270 (DIF) is usually quantified in order to evaluate the increase in the dynamic compressive
271 strength with respect to the static compressive strength for all the concrete mixes with varying
272 rubber contents. DIFs at different strain rates of all the mixes are given in Table 3. The stress
273 strain curves show that normal concrete had the highest dynamic compressive strength
274 followed by 15% and 30% rubberized concrete when compared at the same strain rates because
275 the static strength of the normal concrete was higher than that of the rubberized concrete.
276 However, the DIF of 30% rubberized concrete was the highest followed by those for 15%
277 rubberized concrete and then normal concrete. This observation indicates that the DIF increases
278 with the rubber content and concrete becomes more sensitive to strain rate effect as the rubber
279 content increases. Hence, it also suggests that the addition of rubber in the concrete mix
280 improves the mechanical strength under high loading rates. This increase of the DIF can be
281 explained by the crack arresting mechanism of rubber. When high impact load is applied,
282 cracks start to initiate which passes through the rubber aggregates thus reduces the crack
283 velocity through stress relaxation [36]. In addition, when subjected to dynamic loading, stress
284 wave propagation in rubberized concrete generates friction in the crack interface and any other
285 imperfection and thus results in a partial loss of the impact energy.

286 However, as mentioned earlier, previous studies have reported that an increase in the dynamic
287 compressive strength is not only due to the strain-rate effect especially under high impact
288 loading. Lateral inertial confinement and the end friction produced between the impact bar and
289 specimen also contributes to the increase in the dynamic compression strength, which can lead
290 to overestimating the DIF [45]. In this study, the end friction was minimized by using grease

291 at the two ends of the specimens. Meanwhile, the samples were not tested above the strain-rate
292 of 200 s^{-1} because the effect of the lateral confinement and the end friction becomes inevitable
293 above this strain rate [41]. But according to previous studies [50, 51], there is still contribution
294 of lateral inertial confinement to the DIF that should be eliminated to obtain the true material
295 strain rate effect. The previous study on the DIF of roller compacted concrete, the authors have
296 suggested that the contribution of lateral inertia effect of $\phi 100 \times 50$ samples ranges between 4-
297 13% up to 80 s^{-1} [20] while the corresponding number for $\phi 100 \times 100$ was 13.68% at 200 s^{-1} as
298 reported by Hao et al. [50]. Since the strain rate in this study ranged from 103 s^{-1} to 182 s^{-1} , a
299 reduction factor of 10% caused by the lateral inertia resistance is removed from the testing
300 results.

301 In addition, the energy absorption, which is defined as the area underneath the stress-strain
302 curve of the tested specimen, is computed and shown in Fig. 10. As can be seen from the figure,
303 the energy absorption increased with the strain-rate for the same rubber content while adding
304 rubber to concrete reduced the energy absorption of the rubberized concrete, however, the
305 increment in the energy absorption capacity of the rubber concrete with strain rate is more
306 prominent with the increase in rubber content. For example, when the strain rate increases from
307 103 s^{-1} to 150 s^{-1} , the improvement of the energy absorption of the 15% and 30% rubberized
308 concrete was 18% and 117%, respectively. This observation agrees well with the observation
309 from our previous study [15] but it is different from the conclusion drawn from other studies
310 [12, 46]. In our previous study, Pham et al. [15] carried out drop-weight tests on RuC cylinders
311 and suggested that RuC reduced the maximum impact force, which in turn also led to a
312 reduction in energy absorption capacity although the impact duration was extended, while
313 Gupta et al. [12, 46] found rubberized concrete increased the energy absorption. It is worth
314 mentioning that other previous studies [9, 39] used different types of rubber aggregates, i.e.
315 arbitrary shape and long strip rubber fiber, which may result in distinguished effect. This

316 controversy observation can be explained by combining two effects of rubber aggregates.
317 Firstly, adding rubber improves the energy absorption capacity under high loading rates [12,
318 46], and the rubberized concrete shows more sensitivity to strain-rate. It means the dynamic
319 increase factor of rubberized concrete is higher than that of normal concrete. However, the
320 inclusion of rubber content simultaneously scarifies the compressive strength, which leads to
321 lower energy absorption. Therefore, if the improvement of the energy absorption due to strain
322 rate effect by adding rubber is less than the loss by reducing the compressive strength, the
323 energy absorption of rubberized concrete is less than that of normal concrete. Therefore, the
324 energy absorption capacity of all the specimens is normalized with their compressive strengths
325 and shown in Table 4 and Fig. 11. As can be seen clearly from the figure that the normalized
326 energy absorption of rubberized concrete was significantly higher than that of normal concrete,
327 i.e. at the strain rate of 141-150 s⁻¹, the normalized energy absorption of rubberized concrete
328 was 54-79% higher than that of normal concrete, which are 24 kN/m²/MPa, 37 kN/m²/MPa,
329 and 43 kN/m²/MPa for the specimens with 0%, 15%, and 30% rubber content, respectively.
330 For rubberized concrete with different rubber contents, the normalized energy absorption of
331 30% rubberized concrete was higher than that of 15% rubberized concrete at almost all strain
332 rates except those at 103 s⁻¹. Therefore, it can be suggested that rubberized concrete absorbs
333 more energy than normal concrete at the same compressive strength. Pervious research by
334 Elchalakani [2] showed the RuC with 60 MPa compressive strength can be achieved by adding
335 silica fume.

336 *Rate effects on dynamic properties*

337 The experimental results have confirmed that rubberized concrete is sensitive to strain rate, in
338 which the higher rubber content the higher sensitivity as shown in Fig. 12. The increase of DIF
339 is almost linearly proportional to the rubber content within a wide range of strain rates from

340 103 s^{-1} to 162 s^{-1} . For example, at the strain rate of $124\text{-}131 \text{ s}^{-1}$, the DIF of rubberized concrete
341 increased from 1.52 to 2.54 and 3.21 corresponding to the rubber content of 0%, 15%, and
342 30%, respectively. The rate dependence of concrete behaviour is associated with two
343 mechanisms: (1) the dependence of fracture process on the rate of crack opening and (2) the
344 viscoelastic deformation effect on the intact cement paste [52, 53]. These two mechanisms are
345 important to concrete behaviour but the first dominates at high strain rates, i.e. under impact
346 and blast loads. Najim and Hall [36] carried out experimental testing on the flexural toughness
347 and found that rubberized concrete showed not only a significant increase in the toughness
348 indices but also improvement in crack mouth opening displacement. Meanwhile, Gupta et al.
349 [46] used scanning electron microscopy (SEM) technique to investigate the microcrack
350 propagation and failure of rubberized concrete. These authors mentioned that the mismatch of
351 the elastic modulus between rubber and cement paste may make cracks to pass through rubber
352 aggregates and in turn reduce crack velocity. Their results clearly showed that rubberized
353 concrete reduced the crack opening. Therefore, it indicates that rubberized concrete possesses
354 higher resistance to loading at high loading rates as also observed in the present experimental
355 testing.

356 Liu et al. [34] found that rubberized concrete was less sensitive to strain-rate than normal
357 concrete. This finding is different from the observation in this study where rubberized concrete
358 was found more sensitive to the strain-rate than normal concrete. Liu et al. [34] also observed
359 the DIF significantly increased with the size of rubber aggregates. They used rubber aggregates
360 with a maximum size of 2 mm while the maximum size of 10 mm was used in this study. This
361 difference may explain the significantly higher DIF of rubberized concrete observed in this
362 study as compared to that of normal concrete.

363 The relationship between the DIF and strain rate for the specimens with various rubber contents
 364 is presented in Fig. 13. The figure has shown that the DIF increases with the rubber content
 365 and rubberized concrete is more sensitive to strain rate than normal concrete. The previous
 366 models [49, 50] for normal concrete were also plotted to compare with the DIF of rubberized
 367 concrete. As can be seen that the DIF of rubberized concrete was higher than that of normal
 368 concrete. However, this study covers only a limited range of strain rates from 103 s^{-1} to 182 s^{-1}
 369 ¹. More experimental testing on rubberized concrete at strain rate out of this range is needed.

$$370 \quad DIF_{15\%RuC} = 10^{-4}(\log \dot{\epsilon}_d)^2 - 0.027(\log \dot{\epsilon}_d) + 3.594 \quad \text{for } 165 \text{ s}^{-1} > \dot{\epsilon}_d > 100 \text{ s}^{-1} \quad (4)$$

$$371 \quad DIF_{30\%RuC} = 4 \times 10^{-6}(\log \dot{\epsilon}_d)^2 + 0.012(\log \dot{\epsilon}_d) + 1.474 \quad \text{for } 182 \text{ s}^{-1} > \dot{\epsilon}_d > 100 \text{ s}^{-1} \quad (5)$$

372 The fitted empirical relations of the testing data in this study are given above. These empirical
 373 relations can be used to estimate the DIF of rubberized concrete when predicting the dynamic
 374 responses of structures under high-rate loadings. Meanwhile, the effect of the strain rate on the
 375 Young's modulus and ultimate compressive strain of concrete is also important and worth
 376 further investigations. A previous study has stated that Young's modulus of concrete increased
 377 with the strain rate but at a lower level than that of the compressive strength [21]. Hao and Hao
 378 [45] also confirmed that Young's modulus of normal concrete and fiber reinforced concrete
 379 increases with the strain rate but at a less ratio as compared to that of the compressive strength.
 380 The Young's modulus of all the tested specimens are presented in Fig. 14. As can be seen that
 381 the variation of Young's modulus is quite arbitrary and no definite statement can be made.
 382 There is no consensus on the strain rate sensitivity of the Young's modulus in which different
 383 observations and statements were reported in the literature [21]. For instance, many previous
 384 studies [21, 41, 45] have found that Young's modulus of normal concrete increases with strain
 385 rate while another study stated that an increase of Young's modulus is pseudo-strain-rate
 386 sensitivity [54]. In the meantime, the axial strain at peak stress shows a minor increase with the

387 strain rate but the enhancement is not clear as also mentioned in the previous study. Among
388 those specimens, the axial strain at peak stress of rubberized concrete exhibited a consistent
389 enhancement with strain rate while the trend of normal concrete was unclear as shown in Fig.
390 15. It is worth mentioning that inconsistent observations were reported in the literature, i.e.
391 some previous studies have stated that the axial strain at the maximum stress increased with
392 the strain rate [18, 55] while other studies found it remained almost constant [56] or even
393 declined when the strain rate increased [57, 58]. Further investigations on the effects of strain
394 rate on Young's modulus and axial strain at peak load are indeed necessary.

395 **Conclusions**

396 This study examines the dynamic compressive behavior of rubberized concrete with various
397 crumb rubber contents up to 30% by using SHPB tests. The findings from this study can be
398 summarized as follows:

- 399 1. Rubberized concrete shows great impact resistance under high loading rate. Under the
400 same impact, rubberized concrete still almost intact while normal concrete was
401 fragmented into pieces. Rubberized concrete significantly slowed down the crack
402 propagation and progressive failure as compared to normal concrete.
- 403 2. The experimental results consistently showed that rubberized concrete is sensitive to
404 the strain rate. The higher rubber content, the more sensitive it had to strain rate.
- 405 3. The lateral inertia resistance was quantified from previous studies and then was
406 removed from the experimental results and the DIF formulae for rubberized concrete
407 were proposed.
- 408 4. The absorbed energy normalized using compressive strength of rubberized concrete
409 was 54-79% higher than that of normal concrete.

410 The experimental results showed that rubberized concrete is clearly sensitive to the strain rate.
411 However, this study only covers a range of strain rate from 103 s^{-1} to 182 s^{-1} . Although the
412 results shine some lights on the dynamic material performance of rubberized concrete, further
413 studies on the dynamic material properties of rubberized concrete in a wider strain rate range
414 are deemed necessary.

415 **Conflict of interests**

416 None.

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422

423 **References**

- 424 [1] Gupta T, Chaudhary S, Sharma RK. Assessment of mechanical and durability properties of
425 concrete containing waste rubber tire as fine aggregate. *Constr Build Mater.* 2014;73:562-74.
426 [2] Elchalakani M. High strength rubberized concrete containing silica fume for the construction of
427 sustainable road side barriers. *Structures.* 2015;1:20-38.
428 [3] Elchalakani M, Hassanein M, Karrech A, Fawzia S, Yang B, Patel V. Experimental tests and design
429 of rubberised concrete-filled double skin circular tubular short columns. *Structures: Elsevier;* 2018.
430 p. 196-210.
431 [4] Dong M, Elchalakani M, Karrech A, Hassanein MF, Xie T, Yang B. Behaviour and design of
432 rubberised concrete filled steel tubes under combined loading conditions. *Thin-Walled Structures.*
433 2019;139:24-38.
434 [5] Dong M, Elchalakani M, Karrech A, Fawzia S, Ali MSM, Yang B, et al. Circular steel tubes filled with
435 rubberised concrete under combined loading. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research.*
436 2019;162:105613.
437 [6] Elchalakani M, Hassanein M, Karrech A, Yang B. Experimental investigation of rubberised
438 concrete-filled double skin square tubular columns under axial compression. *Eng Struct.*
439 2018;171:730-46.

440 [7] Atahan AO, Sevim UK. Testing and comparison of concrete barriers containing shredded waste
441 tire chips. *Mater Lett.* 2008;62(21):3754-7.

442 [8] Ozbay E, Lachemi M, Sevim UK. Compressive strength, abrasion resistance and energy absorption
443 capacity of rubberized concretes with and without slag. *Mater Struct.* 2011;44(7):1297-307.

444 [9] Topçu IB, Avcular N. Collision behaviours of rubberized concrete. *Cem Concr Res.*
445 1997;27(12):1893-8.

446 [10] Sukontasukkul P, Chaikaew C. Properties of concrete pedestrian block mixed with crumb rubber.
447 *Constr Build Mater.* 2006;20(7):450-7.

448 [11] Pham TM, Zhang X, Elchalakani M, Karrech A, Hao H, Ryan A. Dynamic Response of Rubberized
449 Concrete Columns with and without FRP Confinement Subjected to Lateral Impact. *Constr Build*
450 *Mater.* 2018;186:207-18.

451 [12] Gupta T, Sharma RK, Chaudhary S. Impact resistance of concrete containing waste rubber fiber
452 and silica fume. *Int J Impact Eng.* 2015;83:76-87.

453 [13] Donga PD, Shah D, Bhavsar JK. Impact Resistance of Waste Rubber Fiber Silica Fume Concrete.
454 *Journal of Civil Engineering and Environmental Technology.* 2016;3(4):274-9.

455 [14] Atahan AO, Yücel AÖ. Crumb rubber in concrete: Static and dynamic evaluation. *Constr Build*
456 *Mater.* 2012;36:617-22.

457 [15] Pham TM, Elchalakani M, Karrech A, Hao H. Axial impact resistance of rubberized concrete
458 with/without FRP confinement for sustainable road side barriers. *Int J Protect Struct.*
459 2019;10(2):154-73.

460 [16] Hao Y, Hao H, Jiang GP, Zhou Y. Experimental confirmation of some factors influencing dynamic
461 concrete compressive strengths in high-speed impact tests. *Cem Concr Res.* 2013;52:63-70.

462 [17] Zhou XQ, Hao H. Modelling of compressive behaviour of concrete-like materials at high strain
463 rate. *International Journal of Solids and Structures.* 2008;45(17):4648-61.

464 [18] Grote DL, Park SW, Zhou M. Dynamic behavior of concrete at high strain rates and pressures: I.
465 experimental characterization. *Int J Impact Eng.* 2001;25(9):869-86.

466 [19] Zhang M, Wu HJ, Li QM, Huang FL. Further investigation on the dynamic compressive strength
467 enhancement of concrete-like materials based on split Hopkinson pressure bar tests. Part I:
468 Experiments. *Int J Impact Eng.* 2009;36(12):1327-34.

469 [20] Wang C, Chen W, Hao H, Zhang S, Song R, Wang X. Experimental investigations of dynamic
470 compressive properties of roller compacted concrete (RCC). *Constr Build Mater.* 2018;168:671-82.

471 [21] Bischoff PH, Perry SH. Compressive behaviour of concrete at high strain rates. *Mater Struct.*
472 1991;24(6):425-50.

473 [22] Ross CA, Tedesco JW, Kuennen ST. Effects of strain rate on concrete strength. *Materials Journal.*
474 1995;92(1):37-47.

475 [23] Rossi P. A physical phenomenon which can explain the mechanical behaviour of concrete under
476 high strain rates. *Mater Struct.* 1991;24(6):422-4.

477 [24] Rossi P. Influence of cracking in the presence of free water on the mechanical behaviour of
478 concrete. *Mag Concr Res.* 1991;43(154):53-7.

479 [25] Eibl J, Schmidt-Hurtienne B. Strain-rate-sensitive constitutive law for concrete. *Journal of*
480 *Engineering Mechanics.* 1999;125(12):1411-20.

481 [26] Aoyama H, Noguchi H. Mechanical Properties of Steel and Concrete Under Load Cycles Idealizing
482 Seismic Actions. AICAP-CEB Symposium on Structural Concrete under Seismic Actions 1979. p. 25-8.

483 [27] du Beton CEI. CEB-FIP model code 1990. *Bulletin d'Information.* 1993;213:214.

484 [28] Ross C. Strain-rate-dependent constitutive equations for concrete. *Journal of pressure vessel*
485 *technology, transactions of the ASME.* 1998;120:398-405.

486 [29] Hao Y, Hao H. Influence of the concrete DIF model on the numerical predictions of RC wall
487 responses to blast loadings. *Eng Struct.* 2014;73:24-38.

488 [30] Zhai C, Chen L, Fang Q, Chen W, Jiang X. Experimental study of strain rate effects on normal
489 weight concrete after exposure to elevated temperature. *Mater Struct.* 2017;50(1):40.

490 [31] Hao Y, Hao H, Jiang G, Zhou Y. Experimental confirmation of some factors influencing dynamic
491 concrete compressive strengths in high-speed impact tests. *Cem Concr Res.* 2013;52:63-70.

492 [32] Pacheco-Torgal F, Ding Y, Jalali S. Properties and durability of concrete containing polymeric
493 wastes (tyre rubber and polyethylene terephthalate bottles): An overview. *Constr Build Mater.*
494 2012;30:714-24.

495 [33] Siddika A, Mamun MAA, Alyousef R, Amran YHM, Aslani F, Alabduljabbar H. Properties and
496 utilizations of waste tire rubber in concrete: A review. *Constr Build Mater.* 2019;224:711-31.

497 [34] Liu F, Chen G, Li L, Guo Y. Study of impact performance of rubber reinforced concrete. *Constr*
498 *Build Mater.* 2012;36:604-16.

499 [35] El-Sherbini Y, Abdel-Gawad A, Shalaby A, El-Gammal A. Compressive strength of concrete
500 utilizing waste tire rubber. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering and Applied Sciences.*
501 2010;1(1):96-9.

502 [36] Najim KB, Hall MR. Mechanical and dynamic properties of self-compacting crumb rubber
503 modified concrete. *Constr Build Mater.* 2012;27(1):521-30.

504 [37] Raffoul S, Garcia R, Pilakoutas K, Guadagnini M, Medina NF. Optimisation of rubberised concrete
505 with high rubber content: an experimental investigation. *Constr Build Mater.* 2016;124:391-404.

506 [38] AS 1012.2. Methods of Testing Concrete; Method 2: Preparation of the Concrete Mixes in the
507 Laboratory. 1994.

508 [39] Pham TM, Elchalakani M, Tran TM, Hao H, Lai J, Ameduri S. Durability Characteristics of
509 Lightweight Rubberized Concrete. *Constr Build Mater.* 2019;224:584-99.

510 [40] AS 1012.9. Compressive strength tests - concrete. 10129: 2014. Sydney, NSW, Australia 2014.

511 [41] Khan MZN, Hao Y, Hao H, Shaikh FUA. Experimental evaluation of quasi-static and dynamic
512 compressive properties of ambient-cured high-strength plain and fiber reinforced geopolymer
513 composites. *Constr Build Mater.* 2018;166:482-99.

514 [42] Lindholm U. Some experiments with the split hopkinson pressure bar. *Journal of the Mechanics*
515 *and Physics of Solids.* 1964;12(5):317-35.

516 [43] Thomas BS, Gupta RC, Panicker VJ. Recycling of waste tire rubber as aggregate in concrete:
517 durability-related performance. *Journal of Cleaner Production.* 2016;112:504-13.

518 [44] Lu YB, Li QM. Appraisal of Pulse-Shaping Technique in Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar Tests for
519 Brittle Materials. *Int J Protect Struct.* 2010;1(3):363-90.

520 [45] Hao Y, Hao H. Dynamic compressive behaviour of spiral steel fibre reinforced concrete in split
521 Hopkinson pressure bar tests. *Constr Build Mater.* 2013;48:521-32.

522 [46] Gupta T, Tiwari A, Siddique S, Sharma RK, Chaudhary S. Response assessment under dynamic
523 loading and microstructural investigations of rubberized concrete. *J Mater Civ Eng.*
524 2017;29(8):04017062.

525 [47] Chen X, Wu S, Zhou J. Experimental and modeling study of dynamic mechanical properties of
526 cement paste, mortar and concrete. *Constr Build Mater.* 2013;47:419-30.

527 [48] Reda Taha MM, El-Dieb A, Abd El-Wahab M, Abdel-Hameed M. Mechanical, fracture, and
528 microstructural investigations of rubber concrete. *J Mater Civ Eng.* 2008;20(10):640-9.

529 [49] Comit Euro-International du Beton. CEB-FIP Model Code 1990. Redwood Books. 1993.

530 [50] Hao Y, Hao H, Li Z-X. Numerical analysis of lateral inertial confinement effects on impact test of
531 concrete compressive material properties. *Int J Protect Struct.* 2010;1(1):145-68.

532 [51] Lu Y, Li Q. About the dynamic uniaxial tensile strength of concrete-like materials. *Int J Impact*
533 *Eng.* 2011;38(4):171-80.

534 [52] Cusatis G. Strain-rate effects on concrete behavior. *Int J Impact Eng.* 2011;38(4):162-70.

535 [53] Bařant ZP, Caner FC, Adley MD, Akers SA. Fracturing rate effect and creep in microplane model
536 for dynamics. *Journal of engineering mechanics.* 2000;126(9):962-70.

537 [54] Li QM, Meng H. About the dynamic strength enhancement of concrete-like materials in a split
538 Hopkinson pressure bar test. *International Journal of Solids and Structures.* 2003;40(2):343-60.

539 [55] Dilger W, Koch R, Kowalczyk R. Ductility of plain and confined concrete under different strain
540 rates. *Journal Proceedings* 1984. p. 73-81.

- 541 [56] Harsh S, Shen Z, Darwin D. Rate sensitive behavior of cement paste and mortar in compression.
542 University of Kansas Center for Research, Inc.; 1989.
- 543 [57] Zhang XX, Rena CY, Ruiz G, Tarifa M, Camara MA. Effect of loading rate on crack velocities in
544 HSC. Int J Impact Eng. 2010;37(4):359-70.
- 545 [58] Wang L-L, Zhou F-H, Sun Z-J, Wang Y-Z, Shi S-Q. Studies on rate-dependent macro-damage
546 evolution of materials at high strain rates. International Journal of Damage Mechanics.
547 2010;19(7):805-20.
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570 Table 1. Mix proportion of all the mixes (kg/m³) [35]

Mixes	Cement (OPC)	Water	Aggregate ≤ 10mm	Aggregate ≤ 7mm	Aggregate ≤ 5 mm	Sand	Rubber crumb (1-5 mm)	Rubber crumb (5-10 mm)
0	426	205	444	306	130	843	0	0
15%RuC	426	205	377	260	111	717	45	58
30%RuC	426	205	311	214	91	500	89	116

571

572 Table 2. Physical properties of crumb rubber

Mechanical Property	Value
Specific gravity (crumb Rubber)	0.54
Fineness modulus (crumb Rubber)	2.36 %
Water absorption % (crumb Rubber)	85 %
Young's modulus @100% (truck tire rubber)	1.97 MPa
Young's modulus @ 300% (truck tire rubber)	10 MPa
Young's modulus @ 500% (truck tire rubber)	22.36 MPa
Resilience @ 23 °C (truck tire rubber)	44 %
Resilience @ 75 °C (truck tire rubber)	55 %
Tension strength (truck tire rubber)	28.1 MPa
Break point strain (truck tire rubber)	590 %

573

574 Table 3. DIF of rubberized concrete with different rubber contents

Strain-rate	Normal concrete	Strain-rate	15% RuC	Strain-rate	30% RuC
116 s ⁻¹	1.49	103 s ⁻¹	2.36	105 s ⁻¹	2.53
125 s ⁻¹	1.52	119 s ⁻¹	2.68	106 s ⁻¹	2.87
140 s ⁻¹	1.69	131 s ⁻¹	2.54	128 s ⁻¹	3.21
165 s ⁻¹	2.30*	150 s ⁻¹	2.87	151 s ⁻¹	3.56
-	-	165 s ⁻¹	3.25	161 s ⁻¹	3.23
-	-	-	-	176 s ⁻¹	3.64
-	-	-	-	182 s ⁻¹	3.86

575 * the DIF was adopted from the tests by Hao and Hao [45]

576 Table 4. Energy absorption of rubberized concrete with different rubber contents

Rubber content (%)	Strain rate (s ⁻¹)	Energy absorption (kN/m ²)	Energy absorption per MPa (kN/m ² /MPa)
0	116	1133	20
	140	1354	24
15	103	881	32
	131	951	34
	150	1037	37
	165	1204	43
30	105	322	20
	128	604	37
	151	698	43
	182	837	51

577